

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17478224

Perception Of Social Studies Teachers On The Influence Of School Environment On Truant Behaviour Among Students Of Junior Secondary Schools In Sokoto Metropolis

Musa Alhaji Sabo¹ & Hussaina Mika'ilu²

¹Department of Social Studies
School of Secondary Education Arts and Social Sciences
Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria

²Department of English
School of Secondary Education Languages
Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study assessed the perception of Social Studies Teachers' on the prevalence of truancy among Junior Secondary School Students with a particular reference to Sokoto Metropolis. It also determined the predisposing factors such as the environmental on truancy behaviours among students. These were with a view to understanding the phenomenon of truancy and devising means of curbing it. The study adopted survey design with population for the study comprised junior secondary school students in the Metropolis of Sokoto State. The sample consisted about Three hundred and eighty-four (384) respondents with three hundred and seventy-two (372) representing students and twelve (12) teachers randomly selected from the population sampled. Five Local Government Areas (LGAs) were selected. 188 Junior secondary schools were selected from the five LGAs. The research instrument titled Questionnaire on Truancy was used to collect data for the study. Data collected were analyzed using percentage and chi-square. It was found from the study that the perception of Social Studies Teachers and Students indicated that the influence of environment had caused many students 77(44.0%) been absent from school without permission from the school authority than female student. Therefore, truancy is prevalent but more among male students than female students. Also, prevalent among students of age range 13-15 years (90.4%). It was also found that student related factor 48.6%, peer related factor 31.4% and school/teacher related factor 14.3% were factors predisposing students to truancy. It was therefore concluded that environment has great deal on truancy behaviours prevalent in junior secondary schools and it is pertinent to understanding truancy and improving school facilities and qualities of guidance and counselling services rendered to curb truancy among school students.

Keywords: Truancy Behaviour, Environment, Teachers Perception and Students.

INTRODUCTION

Education particularly Social Studies is seen as the process of training individuals physically, mentally, emotionally and morally, indeed, it involves a preparation for every facet of living for the satisfaction of the material and spiritual needs, for the growth and development of our personal talent as well as the formation of our personality and characters within the context of the environment. Secondary School education is perceived as the second step in child's educational pursuit. It contributes adequately and effectively for the overall national development. However, teaching and

learning Social Studies are usually taken to be the major activities or process that takes into cognisance students behaviour and its impact on the school environment especially at primary and post primary school levels inside or outside the classroom settings. At the secondary level, the process of imparting knowledge are focus on the specific areas suitable for achieving the goals of Social Studies Education (Okeke, 2021).

However, Social Studies as one of the subjects being taught in our primary schools and junior secondary schools, the method of teaching the subject has not been properly done because most of the teachers handling the subject, have little background or no sound knowledge concerning the strategies and techniques of teaching the subject from lower to high levels (Okam, 2022). These among other things posed problems for the learners in understanding the subject and participate in the class activities .

This study is therefore, designed to assess perception Social Studies Teachers on the Influence of School of environment on truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools with particular a particular reference to some selected Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

Truancy behaviour is one of the problems that exists in our Secondary Schools and affects learners' performance. It is about learners who have not been attending schools regularly as required by the school, expected of them by their parents/guardians and even authorities. The truant behaviour in schools as perceived by many, has constituted a major setback for the individual, the family, the school and the society in general. Although various government have been funding huge sum of money to public on the assumption that there will be learners in schools to be taught about citizen education, spirit of patriotism, national consciousness and the inculcation of the right types of moral values the societies consider necessary for its survival. Therefore, to a larger extent truancy behaviours exhibited by the learners have negative financial implications such as the waste of public resources due to large number of truanting students. Other negative implications include loss of learning opportunities, poor academic performance and eventual school dropout. Truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools may have both short term and long term effects in the society (Hibbett, Fogelman & Manor, 1990).

There is evidence that truancy is linked to environment related factors such as; school location, delinquent behaviours and juvenile crime (Igwe, 2013). It is also perceived that 75% of the truants behaviour associated with the young learners were commonly found in the metropolitan areas where sports and other recreational facilities are present. For examples, Sports viewing centres, motor parks, amusement parks, brothel homes and snooker joints among others (Sara, 2014).

School has been rated by many scholars such as Gambo (2005) as one of the socialization agents in the society. It is a place where instruction, teaching and learning take place. The school is basically a place for preparation for life and where knowledge, disciplined habits of worth and vocational skills are acquired. There is therefore the general belief that the school is an interesting place for children, so it is not abnormal for children to aspire and be anxious as well to attend school. In the opinion of Livingstone (2011) apart from home, the school is the second world of children. At school, for instance, there are more students to play, dance, chat, discuss, and make friends. The school atmosphere should be conducive with beautiful environment, fairly, furnished and well equipped classrooms. In a recent study by Adediran (2021) it was established that students, who perceived that they were in an orderly, organized school and felt a strong affiliation with kind involvement, also reported enhanced self-control, more positive mood and greater peer popularity. It was also argued by Ajagun&Taiwo (2022) that most schools do not provide the right atmosphere, in an interview the have conducted it was found out that students do not like going to schools because of the frequent leisure seeking places in metropolis. Some do not like such schools in rural areas because of the stress, boredom and environmental related factors associated with schools in the cities such as; harsh rules and regulations on students late coming and absenteeism, frequent bullying by senior prefects and sometimes without allowing students to go to school as they like. In a survey conducted by Baker, Sigmon & Nugent (2021) students cited influence of peer groups in Junior Secondary Schools as a key factor in their decision to skip school. They absent themselves from school because they feel that the school is offering them little in terms of extracurricular activities. The findings in this study will leverage on the need why a child must go to school regularly. Having a good Social Studies education will help to give our children the best possible start in life and children who did not attend

school regularly, will not be able to keep up with quality jobs/work, dropout children who have not attended their schools regularly have less chance of getting a good job and young people who are off school for no good reason are at risk of becoming victims of crime or abuse as may also be drawn into anti-social or criminal behavior (Gesinde, 2018).

Objectives of the Study

The main thrust of this study is to access the perception of Social Studies Teachers on the influence of school environment as a correlate of truancy behaviour among students of Junior secondary schools in Sokoto. The specific objectives are To:

- i. Determine the extent of Social Studies Teachers and Students perception on School environment as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis.
- ii. Examine the types of school environment perceived by Social Studies Teachers and Students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis.
- iii. Determine the relationship between students' truancy and Social Studies conducive school learning environment as perceived by Social Studies Teachers and Students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis.

Research Hypotheses

The following three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- HO₁: There is no significant differences between Social Studies Teachers and Students perception on School environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis.
- HO₂ : There is no significant differences between Social Studies Teachers and Students perception on the types of school environment as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis
- HO₃ : There is no significant relationship between students' truancy and Social Studies School conducive learning environment perceived by Social Studies Teachers and students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis.

Review of Related Literatures

Concept of School Environment and its impact on Students learning

School environment consist of both material and non-material resources in the school. It includes the teachers, peers, cohesiveness, the subjects, method of teaching. A healthy and attractive school environment makes for conducive learning and promotes students pride in their schools and their interest to stay in school (Mgbodile 2018). Belanger (2016) writing on the importance of learning environment stated that people's educational life histories are influenced not only by provision of learning opportunities, but also by the quality of the environment where they live or learn. It was also stated that learning is more than education provision and that the community in which learners live have a profound impact on their aspiration to learn, their curiosity and their desire to develop their own competency. Graff (1987) in Nwizu (2016) warned that the environment in which the learner acquires knowledge has a great influence on the cognitive achievement of the learner. It has also been generally agreed that the quality of learning is markedly influenced by environmental and organizational factors. Okafor (2012) opined that learning is an intimate transaction between the learner and his environment. This transaction takes place in a specific context. The child learning in a conducive environment transcends the school parameter. It encompasses the entire community and nation. School environments –wall, ground, lights, and mechanical system can serve as active contributors to the students' learning process. (Keep, 2022). Quisenberry, Eddowesi and Robinson (2021) states that, for individuals to be self-motivating and self imitating, the environment or the setting must be amenable and responsive to human interaction. If the settings do not allow for permeability and malleability, then individual initiative in the learning process is shifted to truancy behaviour. he influence of school location on the achievement of students of public secondary schools has been the concern of many educationists. Bello (2018) opines that school locations are known to influence students learning through quality of teaching staff, class size and availability of infrastructure. The choice and location of school site have been an indispensable aspect of any

effective school planning. This is so because, it is the site that can influence the type of school to be built and the quality and quantity of the buildings. A child's environment that is rural or urban exerts considerable influence on his intellectual development.

Okonkwo (2017) points out that school in rural areas are likely to face the problem of poor academic achievement due to the inequality in provision of human and material resources required for positive educational achievement. This in turn will perpetuate inequality of access to education provision of adequate number and quality of teachers, contents and methods of teaching.

Truancy Behaviour and Students Learning

Truancy behavior has caused a lot of worries to parents, school administrators and society at large. Scholars from the field of education, Social Studies, Sociology and psychology have conceptualized Truancy behavior in different ways. According to Carter (2020) Truancy behavior is a deliberate absence from school without the knowledge of the school authorities or parents. In the same manner, Okonkwo (2017) sees Truancy behavior as "when a student stays away from school without permission, anyone who absents himself from work or duty without good reason or the knowledge of the authority? The above definitions are in agreement that Truancy behavior occurs when a student's absent himself from parent and supposed authority.

According to Huzinga and Thomberry (2020), Truancy behavior is defined as having an unexcused absence from school for one or more part of the day for at least three school days during school weeks. Moreover, Gesinde (2015) defines Truancy behavior as the act when a child, who is believed to have been at school, fails to attend school class without the permission or awareness of the parents or the school authority condemned. Truancy behavior is an international unauthorized absence from school activities. Echebiwe (2019) defined Truancy behavior as a situation when a child under sixteen years of age who is registered at school fails to attend classes without any prior formal permission from the parent or school authority. Therefore, Truancy behavior is the practice of staying away from school without permission. A child who engages in this act is therefore referred to as a truant. This implies that every child is expected to be in school and must be present in school and class attendance. Stoll (2022) conceptualizes Truancy behavior as a situation whereby a student is absent from school for no legitimate reason. He went further to say that many students do skip from lessons or even a full day of school, in most cases, truant students do leave home but will not reach school: they escape from school or class to engage in any other activities that catch up their imagination.

Teachers and educators are the major pillars in the teaching and learning process, they are the most important persons in the practice curriculum. With their knowledge, experience and competencies that are central to any curriculum improvement effort and they are also responsible for introducing the curriculum in the classroom and outside the classroom settings. Researches have shown that the ability of teachers to implement the curriculum is dependent on variables such as teacher qualification, experience, perceptions, students attendance and school support measures among many others (Livingstone, 2011).

According to Gambo (2005) Social Studies teacher-related factors are critical elements influencing student learning outcomes and overall educational quality. One of the primary teacher-related factors is the level of teacher qualification and expertise. Teachers with advanced degrees and specialized training in their subject areas are generally better equipped to deliver content effectively and engage students. Their deeper understanding of the subject matter allows them to present complex concepts in a more accessible manner, which can significantly enhance student comprehension and interest in the subject.

Another vital teacher-related factor is the teacher's instructional strategies and teaching styles. Effective teachers employ a variety of teaching methods to cater to different learning styles and needs of students. This adaptability helps in maintaining student engagement and facilitates better learning outcomes. Techniques such as collaborative learning, hands-on activities, and the integration of technology can make lessons more interactive and enjoyable, thereby fostering a positive learning environment where students will find it very difficult to abscond their classes or schools (Stoll, 2022). Social Studies teacher motivation and commitment also play a crucial role in student achievement. Teachers who are passionate about their profession and show genuine concern for their students' success tend to create a more supportive and stimulating classroom atmosphere. Their enthusiasm can be contagious, motivating students to put forth their best effort. Additionally, teachers who are committed to their own professional development are more likely to stay updated with the latest

The teacher's attitude towards the adult learners and teaching them is very important as it affects how adult learn and thus teaching and learning in adult learning centers. After reviewing many studies, Okam (2022) suggest that it is now a widely accepted those teachers' personally held beliefs and values help to guide their teaching practices. Teaching and learning resources form the medium through which teaching is carried Micheal (2015) assert that implementation demands resources for training, for substitutes, for new materials, for new space and above all for time.

Types of truancy

There are three types of Truancy behavior which are as follows:

1. Habitual Truancy
2. Occasional Truancy
3. Casual Truancy

Habitual Truancy:

This is the type of Truancy behavior that occurs when a student (truant) constantly and continually absent from school without the due knowledge or consent of his parents and school authorities. Habitual truants are mainly those students who miss numerous full days of school academic activities. Their frequencies of absenteeism have become a regular behaviour or habit. It is important to note that students who are habitual truants have high chances of falling behind in their school work, decline in their academic performance and even lose their attachment or positive attitudes towards school (Dimbrsso, 2019)).

Occasional Truancy

This type of Truancy behavior occurs when a student does not constantly and continually absent himself from school. In this type of truancy, the student's level of absenteeism from school without the permission of parents or school authority is irregular or not regular. For instance a child whom the mother refuse going to school and was kept at home to help care for siblings and the child taken out of school for an out-of-season family holiday etc are all instance of occasional truant (Ezeani, 2016).

Casual Truancy

This is the type of Truancy behavior which occurs when the students' absence from school is by chance. This type of Truancy behavior or unexcused absence from school is not regular and constant but happens by chance. For instance students who remained lurking within sound of the school bell, so that they could attend those lessons, which interested them (Ezeani, 2016).

Causes of truancy among Students of Juniou Secondary Schools

Truancy behaviour among students of junior secondary schools in recent times is so alarming and not properly handled would greatly affect the effort of governments in achieving the objectives of secondary education which so much resources has been spent on. On the causes of truancy, authors differ in their opinion as regards to the factors that are responsible for truancy. Evidence from reviewed related literature has indicated that the following factors such as; poor home upbringing, school circumstances, psychological and personality factors, socio-economic situation of the students and societal demands, influence of peer group, social and government influence/factors are the major causes of truancy.

a. Home Upbringing

Tracing the causes of Truancy behavior back to home upbringing, Ezeani (2016) writes"... the truants came from unsatisfactory home situation, families on relief, broken home and the like". In the same vein, Ezekwugo (2015) comments that training of children starts from home and where this is properly done, the foundation laid at home, the school will not find it difficult to continue the education properly. Furthermore, authors stress that in most cases, the seeds of Truancy behavior are laid at home. Odueze (2021), asserts that for education to be real and effective, "there should be sound co-operation between the home and the school. What children need most are parents who can control them. Many are over privileged by been permitted to do as they please. Many parent are afraid to question their Children for not attending schools for sure they do not want the children to felt offended. Also, Children who demand too much of their parents, demand too much of the society. The adult should exert control over children and also to mean the orderly and obedient behaviour that this control is designed to secure.

Still relating home upbringing to students' school behaviour, Shaw as reported by Odueze (2021) states: Whilst few of us would doubt that the main influence on a child's life is his home, that of

school is a good second, the closer the co-operation between these two, the happier must be the child and the more successful his development in every aspect. Although, he brings in the idea of punishment, Odueze emphasizes parents' role in the treatment of a truant. He, in one breath asserts that "corporal punishment leads to Truancy behavior in school and therefore results in acts of indiscipline". And in another breath he holds that punishment should be given to a child but by the parents. This last assertion suggests that the teacher and the parent operate together in the school and that the duty of the parent is to punish the truant while that of the teacher is to teach.

Carter (2020), Odueze, (2021) and Ezekwugo (2015) indicated that the seed of Truancy behavior is laid at home. Poor home upbringing may manifest itself at school in the form of truancy. They emphasize the need for sound co-cooperation between the home and the school for any serious and fruitful tackling of the problem of truancy.

b. School related Factors

In a study carried out by Ogunwe (2016), he pointed out how school factors could contribute to the problem of truancy. To him, some teachers have been found to be very hostile to the children put under their care. Some have been found not to have interest in teaching as a career, some were found not to be attending classes regularly thereby giving room for children to skip classes and develop the habit of Truancy behavior while some teachers have been found to be fond of punishing students for all offences they commit thereby scaring some of them from attending school regularly.

In another study carried out by Ehinmolo (2016) on "perception of classroom Teachers on causes of Truancy behavior and control among secondary school student", the following findings on school factors as the causes of Truancy behavior were made:

a. Educational problem is a cause of Truancy behavior among secondary school students – the educational problem may range from the child not being able to read, write and spell properly to his not being able to assimilate and understand what is read.

b. Disinterest in certain school subjects as a cause of Truancy behaviour– Students' hatred for certain teachers can be a cause of Truancy behavior as the hatred will be brought about through the interaction of students and teachers in the classroom. Also un-stimulating or un-interesting lesson can cause truancy.

c. Distance from school and transportation problems is also causes of Truancy behavior among school children.

Still on school circumstance as a cause of truancy, Dimbrasso (2019) observed in their book "Educational psychology that: In the face of thwarting and distressing school situation, some pupils find that the easiest way out is to keep away from school and some of the children develop hysterical reactions, e.g. some children become ill on examination days.

In a similar manner Ezekwugo (2015) points out that Truancy behavior may be due to the type of teacher posted to a school or the attitude of the teachers towards the students, poor teaching, poor organization, poor attendance of teachers contribute highly to the Truancy behavior of students. She made reference to Simpson's idea that a truant is one who is not happy with schoolwork either because of something is wrong with the school or with pupil himself and instead plans to do something else.

Izuogu (2022) in her own contribution to the causes of Truancy behavior holds that "poor preparation of lessons by teachers, use of abusive words on pupils, frequent use of punishment and too much demand of this or that from the pupils, can contribute to pupils staying away from school. However, facts collected from related literature reviewed indicated that the general school condition has a hand in the cause of truancy.

c. The Environmental related Factors

School environment should be free from barrier or obstacle such as noise, gas/smoke pollutions which could constitute health hazard and in turn affect or reduces students' concentration, perceptual and conceptual focus to learning Sprinthall (1987). Research has shown that markets and garages located near schools have always posed a threat to students. Noise and pollutions from these sources have always endangered students' life and concentration. Therefore, for an effective learning and high academic performance, school in both rural and sub-urban areas should be located off zone, characterized with smoked gas pollutions, market centers or garages. A conducive learning environment stimulates learning understanding and high perception, Sprinthall(1987).

The relationship between school location and students' academic performance has been widely reported. Adepoju(2021), found that students in urban schools manifest more brilliant performance than their rural counterparts. Also, Ogunleye(2022), Nduko(2022), Odueze (2021) and Warwick(2012), reported significant difference in the performance of students in urban and ped-urban areas. However Nwizu (2016) cited in Keep (2022), and Ogunleye (2022) did not found any significant difference in the urban and pen-urban schools.

Dittimiya (2021) in his view on the effects of Truancy behavior maintains that Truancy behavior among students of school aged similar to Junior Secondary Schools have greatly affected the development of human resources needed for social and economic transformation of the society. To him, Truancy behavior is a destructive and undeserving element of progress, training or mode of life. It is an impediment to national development. Truancy behavior allows students to pervert the whole aim of education, examination and public morality it does not encourage development rather it retards progress of the school and the entire society.

In sharing similar view, Durkhein (2020) argues that Truancy behavior is a gateway to serious violent and non-violent crime. To him, students truant act lead to stealing, fighting, drug addictions, destruction of property, sex scandal and armed robbery. Hence when a student is always absent from classes or school environment, what comes to his mind is evil. He plans how to destroy, how to get rich quick and short cut to becomes a millionaire (Uka, 2016).

Also in recent times, high percentages of the crime committed are by students of secondary school according to available literatures, it was discovered that most crimes are committed during school period than holidays; this is because students who engage in truant behaviour are more busy with their parents and guardians during the holidays than when they are in schools (Stoll 2022). The research also discovered that truants behaviours are due to absence from school academic usually repeat classes and even when they are repeating, they do not feel better because they feel that they are too big for such classes. Though few of them (truants) manage to struggle through school and majority of them usually drop out of school if some form of interventions are not taken. Their level of achievement is generally poor because their emphasis is not on academics. They even see school as a form of punishment and something they are doing it not for their sake but to please their parents and guardians. Henry (2017), writes that consequences of Truancy behavior are extensive resulting in negative implications for multiple level of the society and environments. The influences of environment on behavior can be predicted in the maladjustment, poor academic performance, school dropout, drug abuse, delinquency and teenage pregnancy. In the long-run, Truancy behavior predicts poor adult outcome, including violence, marital instability, adult criminality and incarceration.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was adopted for this study. The design fits into this study because it seeks to establish relationship between the variables under consideration which are truancy behaviour and school environment, leadership styles of principals and curricular offerings in the schools as related factors. The target population of the study comprises both students and teachers of Social Studies in Junior Secondary Schools within the metropolis of Sokoto State across the Five (5) Local Government Areas.

Population

The students were estimated to be about four thousand six hundred and sixty four (4,664) students identified by using classroom attendance registers of 188 sampled public Junior Secondary Schools. Out of the total population two hundred and seventy two (272) students and Eighty four (12) teachers were purposely selected for the study from the 188 schools sampled. The schools selected were across the five (5) Local Government Areas that made up of Sokoto Metropolis. Namely; Dange-Shuni, Kware, Sokoto-North, Sokoto-South and Wamakko Local Government Areas of Sokoto State. The sample of the study thus comprises 384 respondents (272 students and 12 Social Studies Teachers).

Table 1: Sampled Population distribution of Social Studies Teachers and Students from Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis Sokoto State

SN	No. of Sch.	No.of Male Teachers	No.of Female Teachers	No.of Male Students	No.of Female Students
8. Dange-Shuni	10	1	-	11	7
9. Kware	18	1	-	20	4
10. Sokoto North	38	2	-	35	5
11. Sokoto South	40	3	-	34	9
12. Wamakko	82	3	2	120	27
Total	188	10	2	220	52

Source: Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education Sokoto 2025

Instrumentation

The instrument was a questionnaire tagged “Environmental Related Factor on Truancy Assessment Questionnaire” (ERFTAQ) developed and constructed by the researchers. It consists of 2 sections A& B. Section A is made up of the respondent's biodata and school address. Section B consists of 16 item statements on truancy behaviour, influence of school environment, perception of Social Studies teachers and students on the variables. The items were placed on four points Likert scale modified Likert four point rating scale of strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagreed (D) respectively.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was validated in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Kaduna State, Department of Psychology and Counselling- It was also given to colleagues in the School of General Education Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto who confirmed its validity.

Pilot Study

It was pilot tested in one Government Girls’ Secondary School (GGC Sokoto) in the Sokoto metropolis using 50 respondents. Test re-test method was used to estimate the reliability and the correlation co-efficient which was found to be 0.89 and was adjudged to be sufficient enough by experts for the study. The researchers used three weeks to collect the data for the study by going round the sampled schools. In each school the respondents were gathered in a separate classroom. Instructions were given on how to fill the questionnaire; forty (40) minutes were also allocated for the exercise which was largely successful. The completed questionnaires were collected instantly in order to avoid delay and misplacement present the population distribution for the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

The data collected from the pilot study was statistically analyzed for the purpose of determining the reliability co-efficient of the instrument. The Cronbach's Alpha technique was used and a reliability index of 0.87 was obtained. These reliability co-efficient was considered adequate for the internal consistencies of the instruments by meeting the conditions of Ajagun & Taiwo (2022), which stated that, an instrument is considered reliable if it lies between 0 and 1, and that the closer the calculated reliability coefficient is to zero, the less reliable is the instrument, and the closer the calculated reliability co-efficient is to 1 the more reliable is the instrument. Hence, the instrument is considered reliable.

Procedure for Data Collection

The data for this study was collected through the administration of questionnaire to the respondents with the support of two research assistants who were trained for three days on the modality for distribution and collection of the instrument on behalf of researcher. The researcher collected an introductory letter from the Department of educational foundations and curriculum, faculty of education, Ahmadu Bello University to the sampled schools. The questionnaire was administered on the respondents from the sampled schools and retrieved back the third day to avoid lost of the instrument.

Procedure for Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used in the analysis of data for this study. The descriptive statistics involve the use of frequencies and percentages for the biodata and other variables, while mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. Also, at inferential statistics level, chi-square was used to test hypotheses 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5. This statistical tool was used because it helps to measure the differences that exist between two (2) variables. It is widely used in social sciences as a measure of the strength of linear dependence between two (2) variables. The data analysis was presented in three main sections. Section one, for bio-data analysis, section two, for answering the research questions and section three, for testing the postulated null hypotheses.

Results

The result of the study in the current research is presented based on the research questions raised and the hypotheses formulated step-by-step: All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

Presentation of Demographic Information

The following tables show the frequencies and percentages of the bio-data of the respondents:

Table 2: Classification of respondents by Status

Status	Frequency	Percentage %
Students	272	70.8
Teachers	12	29.2
Total	384	100

Source: Field Survey July, 2025

Table II shows the classification of the respondents by status where 12 (29.2)% of the respondents are teachers while 272 (70.8)% are students.

Table 3: Gender classification of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Males	330	85.9
Females	54	14.1
Total	384	100

Source: Field Survey July, 2025

Table III shows that out of the three hundred and eighty four (384) respondents that responded to the study, three hundred and thirty (330) representing 85.9% are male while the total of fifty four (54) respondents representing 14.1% are females.

Table 4: Age of the respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage %
10-15years	347	90.4
16-21years	23	6.0
22-27years	0	0.0
28years and above	14	3.6
Total	384	100

Source: Field Work July, 2025

Table IV. presents that the total 347 (90.4%) of the respondents are of 10-15 years of age, while 23 or 6.0% of the respondents are between 16-21 years of age. Also, 14 or 3.6% of the respondents are between 28 years and above.

Table 5: Qualifications of the respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage %
Students	372	90.4
SSCE	2	6.0
NCE	5	1.3
B.Ed	3	0.8
B.Ed	1	0.2
M.Sc/M.Ed and above	1	0.2
Total	384	100

Source: Field Survey July, 2025

Table V shows that, 372 or 96.9% of the respondents are students, while 2 or 0.5% of the respondents are SSCE holders, NCE holders with 5 or 1.3% as holders of Bachelors degree in education. Likewise, 2 or 0.5% have qualifications in Bachelor of Education degree and the few 3 or 0.8% . While 0.2% are holders of Bachelor of Science, Masters of Science, Master of Education and above.

Response to Research Questions

The respondents' opinions on the various research questions raised in chapter one of this study are presented under this section.

Research Question One: *What is the extent of Social Studies Teachers and students perception on School environment as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis?*

Table 6 revealed the opinions of teachers and students on the perception of Social Studies Teachers and Students on the extent of School Environment as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State.

Table 6: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question One

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	2.402	2.03
Students	372	4.317	3.01
Total	384	3.4	2.52

Decision Mean 2.5

Analysis of the above table presents the opinions of teachers and students on a number of item statements as contained in the questionnaire. This table revealed that the total mean of 3.4 was higher than the decision mean of 2.5. By this result, School Environment has greater influenced on students traut behaviour in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State.

Research Question Two: *To what extent are the types of school environment perceived by Social Studies Teachers and Students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state?*

Table 7: shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent to which the types of school environment perceived by Social Studies Teachers and Students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto states.

Table 7: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question Two

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	1.4396	1.0955
Students	372	2.69	1.1679
Total	384	2.1	1.1317
Decision Mean 2.5			

Table 7 depicts the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the extent to which social studies teachers and students perceived types of school environment perceived by Social Studies Teachers and Students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State. The table revealed that the total mean of 2.1 was lower than the decision mean of 2.5. This result shows that social studies teachers and students are not well equipped in perceiving the types of school environment as related truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State.

Research Question Three: *How conducive is social studies school learning environment in the Students truant behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State?*

Table 8. revealed the opinions of the respondents on how social studies school learning environment influences truant behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State.

Table 8: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question Four

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	2.68	1.1679
Students	372	2.7396	1.0955
Total	384	2.71	1.1317

Decision Mean 2.5

Table 8 revealed the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the social studies school learning environment influences truant behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State. The table revealed that the total mean of 2.71 was higher than the decision mean of 2.5. This means that there is a significant difference between social studies conducive school learning environment and truant behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State.. Therefore, the respondents were of the view that they often use classroom, library, playing ground and assembly hall, while enough windows, lightening and toilet are not adequately provided and as such it affects students' enrollments.

Hypotheses Testing

All the five null hypotheses were tested at alpha 0.05 level of significance using chisquare statistics.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the School environment and truant behaviour among junior secondary school in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state. Table 9 revealed the

opinions of teachers and students on the influence of School environment and trauant behaviour among junior secondary school in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state.

Table 9: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between Social Studies Teachers and Students perception on School environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis.

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX2	α	df	CritiX2	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	2.402	2.03	21.47	0.05	5	12.43	0.001	Rejected
Students	372	4.317	3.01						
Total	384	3.4	2.52						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

Results of the chi-square statistics on table 9 revealed that $P < 0.05$ because the X^2 obtained (21.47) is greater than critical X^2 (12.43), this means that there is a significant difference between School environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between types of school environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state.

Table 10 shows the opinions of teachers and students in respect of the difference between types of school environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state.

Table .10: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between types of school environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX2	α	df	CritiX2	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	1.439	1.0955	9.245	0.05	5	15.391	0.710	Retained
Students	372	2.69	1.1679						
Total	384	2.1	1.1317						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

The result on table 10 shows that X^2 calculated of 9.245 was less than the critical X^2 of 15.391 under 5 df, under 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X^2 was less than the critical X^2 , the decision was to accept the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between types of school environment perceived by Social Studies Teachers and Students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between social studies conducive School learning environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state.

Table 11 shows the opinions of teachers and students on the difference between social studies conducive School learning environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state.

Table 11: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between Social Studies Conducive learning environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX2	α	df	CritiX2	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	2.32	0.173	18.20	0.05	4	26.412	0.217	Retained
Students	372	2.10	1.14						
Total	384	2.2	0.6565						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

Table 11 shows that X2 calculated of 18.20 was less than the critical X2 of 26.412 under df of 4, and 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X2 was less than the critical X2, the decision was to accept the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between social studies conducive School learning environment and truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state.

Summary of Major Findings

The following are the findings of the study based on the hypotheses tested:

1. Findings in this research revealed that there is a significant difference between the school environment and truant behaviour among junior secondary schools in the study area. Therefore the Null hypotheses was rejected.
2. Finding also revealed that there is no significant difference between types of school environment and truant behaviour among junior secondary schools in the study area. Therefore, the Null hypotheses was retained.
3. Findings from the study showed no significant difference between social studies school conducive learning environment and truant behaviour among junior secondary schools in the study area. The Null hypotheses was accepted.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

In view of the hypotheses tested and answers to research questions, the following are the discussions of findings. Results of the chi-square statistics on table 9 revealed that $P < 0.05$ because the X2 obtained (21.47) is greater than critical X2 (12.43), there is a significant difference between the school environment and truant behaviour among junior secondary schools in the study area. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was rejected. Also, the descriptive analysis of teachers and students on a number of item statements as contained in the questionnaire revealed that the total mean of 3.4 was higher than the decision mean of 2.5. By this result, School environment can influence students' behaviour whether positive or negative. This finding supported the claims of Tunarie (2000) that, learners without school environment are hopeless and school environment without learners are useless.

The result on table 10 shows that X2 calculated of 9.245 was less than the critical X2 of 15.391 under 5 df, under 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X2 was less than the critical X2, the decision was to accept the hypothesis which states that which states that there is no significant difference between types of school environment perceived by Social Studies Teachers and Students as related to truancy behaviour among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto state. Similarly, table depicts the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the extent to which types of school environment influenced truant behaviour as perceived by the respondents in the study area.

The table revealed that the total mean of 2.1 was lower than the decision mean of 2.5. This result shows that truant behaviour among students in junior secondary schools depend largely on the types of school environment. This finding correlate with the finding of Baker & Jansen (2022) which revealed that truant behaviour exhibited by learners depend largely on the types of the school environment either boarding school, day-school, co-educational settings, Girls Colleges and Boys Schools. Shuaibu (2011) also opines that truancy behaviour among students differ from one school to another, environment and vice-versa.

Table 11 shows that X2 calculated of 18.20 was less than the critical X2 of 26.412 under df of 4, and 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X2 was less than the critical X2, the decision was to accept the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between social studies

school conducive learning environment and truancy behaviour among students of junior secondary schools in the Sokoto Metropolis.

Table also shows the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the extent to which social studies school conducive learning environment and truancy behaviour among students of junior secondary schools in the Sokoto Metropolis correlated. The table revealed that the total mean of 2.2 was lower than the decision mean of 2.5. This means that the conducive learning environment always promote students learning and motivates students to learning. Majority of the respondents were of the opinion that modern instructional materials like radio, television, tap recorder, projector, slides, computer, video, decoder, sports facilities and students common room when available, can retained students population and enrollment. While the few of them greed that charts and textbooks are more often used while teaching social studies and classroom were not attractive, poor ventilations and challenges of students toilets (especially female students). Also, some of the respondents agreed that This study is share the same findings with Baker (2013) which revealed that, conducive social studies school learning environment cannot be effectively utilized without the use of instructional materials, excursion/ field trips, projects and group activities that keep students motivated.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study the following conclusions are hereby drawn:-

Truancy behaviour among Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State is a widespread phenomenon as no single Secondary School is said to have escaped. Most of the secondary schools in the metropolitan city of the State, are associated with unfavourable environment for learning and this aided truancy behaviour by the students. It was also discovered that three types of school environments are discernible in the schools located in: urban, semi-urban and rural areas with different traunt behaviour among students in the study area which did not have the same bearing on truancy behaviour of the students. The social studies curriculum offerings in the state junior secondary schools level are not adequate as most teachers employed to teach social studies are not well grounded on the pedagogical skills and technical know-how on the creation of conducive social studies school learning environment that denounces any form of truancy behaviour among Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of study, the researchers therefore offered the following recommendations:

1. The authorities should provide conducive learning environment with state of art facilities that will engages of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
2. Punishment of students, by school prefects or teacher- students as well as bullying by student-student should be placed on proper footing and halted. Most of the students ran aware from schools as a results of corporal punishments and hard labour by senior prefects, teachers and principals.
3. Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State should consider it necessary to be reviewing its Social Studies syllabus from time to time and ensure that competent teachers are employed to teach the subject for better orientation and understanding of the subject. This will boost students morale and curiosity in the choice of the subject.
4. There is need for government to provide toilets and other social facilities that will keep the students indoors especially toilets for female students that could check the excesses of the truants among the male and female students.
6. There is need for a Guidance and counseling centre in each of the Secondary School in Sokoto State to enable students familiarize for vocational and personal-social guidance that could also check the excesses of the truants behaviour as a result of students maltreatment.

REFERENCES

- Adediran. H. (2021). Truancy, Absenteeism and Delinquency among School Children: *Scottish Educational Studies*. 114-119.
- Adeduran, A. (2021). *The Importance of Teachers Teaching Methods on Academic Performance of Secondary School Science Students*. Ijebu-Ode Ogun State: Ego Booster Books.

- Adeyemi, J. N.(2019). *Truancy behaviourr eduction: keeping student in school*. Ikeja: Malthouse press.
- Adepoju,O.(2021). *A comparative study of students Academic Performance and behaviour maladjustment: Ibadan*; City Printing Press Ltd.
- Ajagun, S. F.& Taiwo, S. A. (2021). Effects of Peer Assisted Learning On Academic Performance *Journal of education science & (4) 34- 55*
- Keep, H.(2022). *A critical analysis on the effects environment, Truancy behaviour and cultism on the future aspiration of Nigeria students a serious threat to parents expectation*. An Unpublished paper; Enugu.
- Graff, A.(1987). Psychodemographic predictors of school attendance Behaviours among secondary school students in Osun state, Nigeria. *The social science year, 4(6), 602-672*.
- Baker, D.& Jansen. J. (2022). Using groups to reduce elementary school absenteeism. *Social Work in Education, 22(1) 46-53*.
- Baker, M.L, Sigmon, J.N, & Nugent, M.E.(2021,). *Truancy behaviour in education: keeping student in school*. Retrieved from <http://www.ncjrs.gov/pdffiles1/ojdp/188947.pdf>
- Bellanger,I.(2016). Adolescent Development, New York: McGraw Hill Book Company inc.
In public examination in secondary schools in ondo and Ekiti state, *Nigeria current research Journal on Economic Theory, 3(2), 36-42*.
- Bello, H. (2018). Influence of Students Engagement on Academic Achievement of Students *International Referred Research Journal, 3(30), 32-33*.
- Boga, I.J.(2013). *The effects of Truancy behaviouon Academic Performance of secondary school students in Ukum Local Government Area* Bsc project, Unpublished. Sociology Department, University of Mkar.
- Carter, K.J. (2020). *Manual to combat Truancy*. New York. McGraw Hill Book Company inc.
- Dimbrsso, T.S. (2019). *Understanding female Students Academic Performance: An Exploration of Situation in South Nations Nationality and people Regional State*. Ethiopia: International Institute of Social Science.
- Dittimiya. I. A.(2021). Discipline in schools in Pertomode, V.F.(Edd) Introduction Planning and Supervision. Lagos Joja Press Limited.
- Durkhein, E. (2020). *Suicide Landon: Rut"lodge press*.Education Studies; Truancy behaviours a contextual and school- Related problem; A comparative multilevel Anaiysis of country and school characteristic on civic knowledge among Fourteen year olds"; Ellen claes, et al; May 2019.
- Echebiwe, G.(2021). *Effects of Delinquency on Academic Achievement London: London Social Printing press*.
- Ehinmolo S. (2016). *Effects of students absenteeism: the Under achievement of student*. Boston: Harvard university press.
- Ezeani N.(2016). *Truancy behaviour among Secondary School Students, A. Multi-disciplinary Approach*, Umuachi: Versatile print.
- Ezekwugo, V. (2015). *The Effects of Truancy behavior on the Effectiveness of Teachers in primary school in Awkunanaw Community of Nkanu West Local Government*. Unpublished Tesis. University of Nigeria Nsukka.
- Mgbodile,S .(2018). Truancy, its measurement and causation: A brief Review of the Literature. London: Her Majestys Stationary Office.
- Gambo, A. H. (2005). *Social studies education and socialization process: An unpublished lecture notes: Zaria; ABU*
- Gesinde, A. M.(2015). Psycho-Social Determinants of Truant Behaviour among secondary school students. Ife psychologia: *An International Journal Vol13, no 1, pp.188-199*.
- Gesinde, A. M. (2018). Psycho-social Dtermination of Truant Behaviours among Secondary School Students. Ife psychologia: *An international journal, 13(1), 188-199*.
- Henry, K.L.(2017). Who's Skipping school: Characteristics of Truants in 8th and 10th Grade? *The Journal of school health, 77,29-35*.
- Hibbett,A, Fogelman, K.& Manor, O.(1990). Occupation outcome of Truancy. *British journal of educational psychology.60, 23-26*.

- Huiziaga, D. & Thornberry, T.P. (2020). Co-occurrence of Delinquency Initial Findings. Washington, DC: U.S. Dept. of Justice, office of Juvenile Justice.
- Igwe, E. U. (2013). Effect of Individual and Group Counselling on Secondary School Students' Truant Behaviour in Abia State. *An International Multidisciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*, 7, (2).
- Izuogo, E. (2022). *Truancy: First step to lifetime of problem*. Official Bulletin of Juvenile and Delinquency Prevention. OJJDP: us Department of Justice.
- Livingstone, W. (2011) Socialization Process in Nigeria. Unpublished lecture notes; Zaria, ABU
- Micheal, G.H (2015) Perspectives on Absenteeism High in school. *A Journal of Sociology*, (2): 29-38.
- Nduko, S. (2021). Exploring Students' Engagement in Learning practices *Journal for Higher Education Learning* 7(1), 36-43.
- Nwizu, S. (2016). *The Role of Peer Assisted Learning in the Performance of Students in Secondary Schools*. Longman publishing, New York, USA.
- Ogunwe, I.A (2016). *Discipline in school in peretomode, introduction to Educational Administration, planning and supervision*. Lagos: Joja press Limited.
- Odunze, B.L.(2021). The causes of Truancy behavior among primary school pupils in Mbano Local Government Area if Imo State Unpublished m.s.c thesis.
- Ogunloye, W. (2022). Student Attendance and absenteeism. Dropping out how much do school contribute to the problem. *Teacher college Record*. 87(3), 374-392.
- Okam, C.C.(2022) The Status of Social Studies as Curriculum Design for Exploring Family Life Education for National Transformation: *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies and Civic Education*; Vol.3(1) pp 39-57.
- Okafor, R.(2012). *The school Attendance and Discipline* Lagos: Nigerian University publishing Ltd.
- Okeke, E. (2021) Promoting Collaborative Teaching in Social Studies Education in Nigeria: A theoretical Perspective: Enugu; University of Nigeria Nsukka Press.
- Okonkwo, S. (2017). *Influence of Environment on School Absenteeism and Truancy, Cross Cultural Perspective*, Onitsha: Leo Tina Press Ltd.
- Quiseberry, S. Eddowesi, N.& Robinson, A.(2021). Absenteeism and Truancy. In E.O.Obe(Ed) *school Discipline and Remedies*. Lagos: Premier press and Publishers.
- Sara, S. S. (2014). Effectiveness of Reality and Behaviour Therapy in the Treatment of Truancy among Students of Government College Birnin Kudu, Jigawa State Nigeria. Unpublished Doctoral thesis, University of Maiduguri.
- Shuaibu, S. (2011). *The Incidence of Truancy among Nigeria Youth: Implication for Counseling*. Jos University Press Limited.
- Sprinhall, O. (1987). *Self- concept and Academic Achievement. Slovenia and France*. Personality and individual Differences, 30: 887-899.
- Stoll, H. (2022). *Outsiders: studies in Sociology of Deviance*. New- York: Free press
- Tunarie, J. O. (2000). *Fundamentals of Research Methodology*, Ilorin: Victory Publications Ltd
- Udo, A. (2016). Access Programmes and Higher Education Outcomes. *Science insights on higher Education policy in Ireland (pp. 143–164)*. Springer.
- Udueze, V. K. (2021). A conceptual model of non-traditional undergraduate student attrition. *Review of Educational Research*, 55(4), 485–540.
- Uka, N.(2016). *Essentials of foundation of educational through and practices of Classroom Management and Control*. Lagos: Nigeria education research council.
- Warmick, J.(2012). School Characteristic that influence students attendance experience of students in a school avoidance program. *High school Journal*, 19,12-24.